

**An Analysis of a Single Case Report on Malaria and its Impact on
Clinical and Administrative Decision Making.**

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Abstract

Case reports often draw attention to clinical problems that have not been answered in current medical literature and guidelines. They can provide direction for future study designs, and can provide the first evidence for hitherto unknown and/or unanswered medical and clinical problems. Clinical guidelines as published by competent authorities are based on the best available data and so can be deficient in addressing uncommon presentations of a clinical problem. The epidemiology of malaria follows a highly varied pattern in different parts of the world. The interactions between the agent, vector, host, and reservoir, produces different risk profiles, and the prognosis can be difficult to predict. Hence, for treatment purposes malaria guidelines should be complimented by the judgement of the treating clinician, after he/she weighs in the available data, and assesses the context and any out of pattern findings.

Introduction

In the age of randomized controlled trials(RCTs),¹ case reports(CRs) can still play a significant role in providing insight into clinical problems that do not fit into known patterns.^{2 3} It may also be the first link in the chain of evidence that guides further study designs, and may bring attention to as yet unravelled medical conditions and related clinical knowledge. Medical and clinical guidelines are based upon study designs that are inferential in nature, and may not be able to address the entire gamut of case scenarios, that may emerge, from time to time.⁴ The author undertook a detailed analysis of a CR, and reviewed related medical literature to understand the relevance and utility of the information presented in furthering medical knowledge and clinical management of malaria.⁵ A critical appraisal of clinical guidelines in general and specific to the clinical condition under review was also taken into account.⁶

1. Study Background

- a. Study Design-** The authors have presented a CR, to the journal in October, 2007 dealing with the dual infection of falciparum and vivax malaria. The report has followed currently accepted framework for CRs and the information has been presented in appropriate sections. CRs, in general are limited by the fact that rigorous methodologies of other epidemiological research study designs are largely absent. The issues of randomisation, control, cohorts, sampling, data collection and analyses, remain beyond scope. Nevertheless, CRs may be successful, in pointing out the lacunas in the current understanding of a known medical condition, and the clinical problems associated with it.⁷ This in turn may fuel further research using more expansive methodologies and methods within the framework of appropriate study designs.

This CR deals with a patient (PB) who did not fit in the then clinical classification of severe malaria, but had ominous microscopy findings. The treating clinician (TC), decided to initiate parenteral therapy generally reserved for cases classified as severe malaria and has provided a

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timeline of events. The authors have included an additional table, which details relevant microscopy findings and parasitaemia calculations of a comparable cohort. Additional information, as to how the table was compiled and quality assurance of the findings, would bolster the CR.⁸

- b. WHO malaria guidelines 2016⁹**-It will be pertinent at this point to inform the reader regarding the revised version of the original guidelines (2006)¹⁰ which was referred to in the CR being discussed.

Key Recommendations

Diagnosis: All suspected cases of malaria to undergo a parasitological test (microscopy/Rapid Diagnostic kit) to confirm the diagnosis, and should be supported by a quality assurance programme.

Uncomplicated *P. falciparum* malaria

Treatment (excluding special risk groups): 3-day artemisinin-based combination therapy (ACT)

Reducing transmissibility: Single dose of .25 mg/kg bw Primaquine with ACT in low-transmission areas.

Treatment in Special Risk Groups:

Non-immune Travellers returning to non-endemic settings: ACT

Hyperparasitaemia: ACT with close monitoring for treatment failure and clinical deterioration.

Uncomplicated malaria(others)

Uncertain species: ACT

Area with chloroquine susceptibility: Chloroquine or ACT

Area with chloroquine resistance: ACT or Quinine (for pregnant women in first trimester)

Prevention of relapse (*P. vivax/ovale*)

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G6PD status required.

14-day course of .25/mg bw Primaquine in all settings

In G6PD deficiency: .75mg/kg bw weekly for 8 doses with close monitoring.

Severe Malaria

IV/IM artesunate for at least 24 hours and then oral therapy with ACT (3 days) and primaquine. Consider artemether in preference to quinine when artesunate is not available.

Situation after 2006-The WHO develops guidelines using specific study designs, data collection and analyses, which then passes through multiples reviews and checks. As a result, the quality of evidence and strength of recommendations, has seen a breakdown into scales as they are dependent on the relative merit of data available.¹¹

Situation after 2015¹²-WHO, in its most recent guidelines have acknowledged that recommendations for uncomplicated malaria based on these additional microscopy findings, would be difficult to formulate due to several factors. An accurate quantitative technique is required, the risk of severe malaria varies according to the epidemiological context,¹³ and the factors that decide treatment failure and therapeutic responses remains largely unknown. WHO advocates close monitoring, and prompt initiation of parenteral therapy in such situations. Experts have opined to use much lower thresholds of parasitaemia, to define severe malaria independent of the clinical picture.¹⁴

c. Relevance to the study setting- The PB being discussed is from the Thai-Burmese border, which is characterised by low but sustained transmission rates,¹⁵ and some of the highest case fatality rates for patients of uncomplicated malaria with high parasitaemia.¹⁶ Immunity development is hampered in such settings, and all age groups are at risk of developing severe malaria.¹⁷ As the authors have pointed out, cases can present with microscopy findings that do not clinically reflect the severity of infection. The then WHO guidelines (2006) had included

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hyperparasitaemia as a criterion for severe malaria and indication for parenteral therapy, but the blood picture of the PB fell short of the cut-off value. As detailed in the timeline, the PB began to manifest signs of severe malaria, even on parenteral therapy. The authors have mentioned additional microscopy findings of peripheral schizonts and other mature forms, and has opined that these findings to be the harbinger of poorer prognosis. A statement from the WHO guidelines (2006) mentions appearance of more mature forms in blood as an indicator of poor prognosis, but was not part of any formal recommendation.

Complex pathophysiological mechanisms, along with endemicity, pattern and intensity of transmission, and residency status of an individual, creates varied risk profiles in different parts of the world. So, a study in contrast are regions of Middle-East and North Africa, which are non-endemic for malaria. Patients in these areas, would be non-immune to malaria parasites, and would generally present or develop early severe malaria,¹⁸ and the blood picture may show high parasitaemia and schizont count.

1. Case Presentation¹⁹:

A similar clinical case, presenting in an endemic high-transmission region, will still need to undergo risk stratification using complementary blood microscopy and knowledge of the residence status of the patient.

Treatment²⁰

- a. Resident, uncomplicated malaria with low parasitaemia and low schizont count: Oral ACT with or without primaquine.
- b. Resident, complicated malaria or uncomplicated malaria with high parasitaemia and high schizont count and intraleukocytic hemozoin: IV ACT and then oral ACT.

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- c. Non-resident, uncomplicated malaria: Oral ACT. Close observation for clinical deterioration. If high parasitaemia and schizont count is found, to consider initiation of parenteral therapy, even in the absence of clinical deterioration.^{21 22}
- d. Non-resident, complicated malaria:²³ IV artemisinin, followed by national policy.
- e. In all cases, the TC to maintain low thresholds and high suspicion, to determine appropriateness of initiation of parenteral therapy.

2. Interpretation of Results

a. Important messages:

1. A case of malaria can present with a clinical picture, which is inconsistent with the severity of ongoing infection.
2. In blood microscopy, levels of parasitaemia, peripheral schizont count and appearance of other mature forms, should be considered as risk factors of poor prognosis. Hemozoin pigment in neutrophils is another indication of ongoing severe infection.
3. A decision to initiate early therapy using parenteral medications could potentially prevent or mitigate severe symptoms and signs, and lead to prevention of complications, and early recovery.
4. Information regarding the endemicity, transmission pattern and rates, and residence status of the patient are complimentary to the decision-making process.
5. An understanding of the pathophysiological mechanisms will shed further light on a given atypical case.
6. A thorough understanding of how clinical guidelines are developed and the level of evidence and strength of recommendations, should be borne in mind.

b. Emergency Bulletin: Proposed additions to the National Malaria Case Management Guidelines (April,2008, MoPH, Thailand)

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1. These guidelines should be considered as an addition to the most recent WHO publication, and to be used to better address cases that originate near the Thai-Burmese border, and may be extended countrywide based on further transmission data available.
2. All suspected cases should undergo a microscopy test to ascertain the load of parasitaemia and presence and load of schizonts and other peripheral mature forms. Intranuclear pigment detection remains important to add to the clinical picture.
3. The decision to initiate early parenteral therapy with artemisinin or its derivatives, remains the sole discretion of the treating clinician.
4. Periodic blood microscopy should be used to monitor response to treatment.
5. An ACT regimen, with a suitable partner drug/s, must be used to complete the treatment.

Rationale:

1. There have been a case report from the western border areas, of a patient who did not meet the criteria of severe malaria as led down by WHO, and whose clinical picture belied the underlying severity of the disease.²⁴ A larger study done in 1997, indicates that the mortality due to hyperparasitaemia near the Thai-Burmese border areas(TBBA), are significantly higher, even in the absence of initial clinical features of severe malaria.¹⁶ Several other studies have identified cross border areas to be the hotspot for infection in non-immune persons and similar high mortality for cases originating near the TBBA.^{25 15}
2. Previous studies, have opined that a positive relationship exists between parasitaemia detected in peripheral blood, and ongoing infectious activity of *P. falciparum*, and negatively affects the prognosis.^{26 27} Currently there is no consensus regarding what parasitaemia index classification should be used for predicting severity of infection, and the correlation seems to be based on local endemicity and transmission patterns.²⁸ The presence of schizonts and more mature forms in peripheral smear are considered to be an even more important prognostic

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marker.^{29 30} Hemozoin pigment in peripheral leukocytes additionally indicates the degree of central sequestration, and effective biomass.^{31 32}

3. The current WHO guidelines (2006) are developed on data available from large studies, but still may not provide complete information of the conditions prevailing near the TBBA.³³ Malaria can rapidly progress to overwhelm the organ systems of the body,³⁴ and the decision to delay parenteral therapy carries much higher risk, if the condition is allowed to progress.³⁵

Situation after 2006: In the handbook of severe malaria treatment,³⁶ WHO does not mention any contextual limitations of the treatment protocols.

Situation after 2012: In the revised version of the handbook,³⁷ WHO has recommended to maintain a low threshold while considering cases to have a poorer prognosis. Nothing should delay the initiation of parenteral artemisinin, if the treating clinician is concerned regarding the true picture of ongoing infectious activity. There has been concerns, that enough data was not available during the 2006 guidelines, and certain parameters needs to be modified, in the light of new and local findings available.³⁸

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